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ABSTRACTS

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the average walking speed in the experimental group was 0.6 m/s, increased to 0.77 m/s after exercise and maintained at a level of 0.69 m/s after six months. The difference between the results was statistically significant ($p=0.002$). In the walking speed a significant improvement was obtained after the exercise program in the control group but after six months, the average walking speed was close to the value before the start of the program. The distance in the experimental group has been improved and was 18,6 meters and was statistically significant. *Conclusions:* The exercise program and gait training after stroke with using treadmill have an impact on a significant gait improvement in both groups. In the late period an improvement in the exercise group on a treadmill with biofeedback has been shown.

PO-1340

PREDICTORS OF THERAPY RESPONSIVENESS FOR A MULTIMODAL THERAPY CONCEPT AND AEROBIC TRAINING IN BREAST CANCER PATIENTS WITH CHRONIC CANCER-RELATED-FATIGUE

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Background Cancer-Related-Fatigue (CRF) and insomniac sleep disturbances are the most frequent and burdensome symptoms of disease-free breast cancer patients (BC). Non-pharmacological treatments such as aerobic training (AT) and sleep (SE) are the treatments with the best evidence. In this pilot-study we tested beside the implementation of a new multimodal concept of therapy (MM), consisting of SE, psycho-education, eurhythm and painting therapy and its comparison to AT which questionnaire is the best predictor for the treatment responsiveness. *Methods:* At the Gemeinschaftskrankenhaus Havelhöhe and the Hannover Medical School 31 out of 34 patients suffering from BC and CRF could be fully evaluated in a ten-week intervention study; 21 of them chose MM and 10 decided for AT. CRF was measured with the help of the Cancer Fatigue Scale (CFS-D). Beside the CFS-D we captured by questionnaire the Pittsburgh Sleep-quality-index (PSQI), autonomic regulation (aR), self-regulation (SR), internal coherence (ICS) and quality of life with EORTC-QLQ C30. Statistics SPSS 19.0. *Results:* We tested the correlations of baseline PSQI and EORTC subscales emotional, physical, role functioning and global health with CFS-D at baseline ($R^2=0.02 - 0.40$) and at the end of the intervention ($R^2=0.05 - 0.24$). Baseline aR, SR and ICS correlated with CFS-D with $R^2=0.27, 0.17$ and 0.44 at baseline and with $R^2=0.22, 0.38$ and 0.48 at the end. Participants with high SR or ICS and high CFS-D at baseline had the best CRF improvement after the intervention. *Conclusion:* This pilot-study supports the hypothesis that questionnaires measuring adaptive capacities such as self-regulation and internal coherence are more appropriate as outcome predictors than classical HRQL or sleep questionnaire for educative intervention studies

PO-1341

PATELLAR TENDON RUPTURE: A RARE COMPLICATION OF TOTAL KNEE REPLACEMENT

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Objective: To present a rare complication of total knee replacement *Methods:* Total Knee Replacement (TKR) is the procedure of choice for patients with advanced knee osteoarthritis when non surgical treatment options fail. Complications of TKR include infection, deep vein thrombosis and joint loosening. A rare but debilitating complication is patellar tendon rupture, which may be due to inherent weakness of the tendon and damage to the tendon during surgery or trauma. We report a case of patellar tendon rupture after TKR in a 75 years old female. On post operative day 22, she experienced excruciating pain in the left knee while getting up from a low lying commode chair and was unable to stand without assistance. Clinical examination revealed patellar tendon rupture and radiographs confirmed patella Alta. Site of rupture was confirmed by MRI and musculoskeletal ultrasound. *Results:* Patellar tendon repair surgery was done using semitendinosus graft followed by knee immobilization for six weeks. Rehabilitation was continued for twelve weeks. Patient was able to walk with cane and was independent in activities of daily living. *Implications/Impact on rehab:* Patellar tendon rupture is a rare complication of total knee replacement surgery. Care should be taken before, during and after surgery. Low lying commode chairs and commode can lead to rupture of an already compromised tendon. Clinical examination and radiographs can confirm the diagnosis. Surgical repair is the only option for treatment. Prognosis is usually not good.

PO-1342

EVALUATION OF SLEEPINESS IN PATIENTS WITH THORACIC OUTLET SYNDROME

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Objective: Thoracic Outlet Syndrome (TOS) is one of the most common syndromes of compromised circulation in the cervical region. The aim of the study was to evaluate the sleepiness in patients with diagnosed TOS. *Methods:* 100 patients (26.7% males and 73.3% females) aged 51.11 (28-84) with diagnosed TOS were evaluated. All patients filled a questionnaire about their quality of sleeping and Epworth sleepiness scale. *Results:* 55.6% of patients evaluated their state of health as moderate and 73.3% of them evaluated their pain as moderate. 84.4% of patients indicated that they had some problems with sleeping- half of them have subject impression of permanent problem with sleeping. According to the Epworth scale 35,6% had some problem with sleepiness but patient's subject impression of having sleeping problem was not correlate ($r=0.048; p=0.755$) with result of observed sleepiness problem on Epworth scale. Patient's evaluation of pain statistically significant ($r=-0.316; p=0.034$) correlate with sleepiness. Results pointed that the most problematic sleepiness factor was "lying down to rest in the afternoon when circumstances permit" ($r=0.760; p=0.000$) and the least problematic was "sitting and talking to someone" ($r=0.349; p=0.019$). One statistically significant canonical correlation ($F=0.907; p=0.000$) was observed which pointed that predictor of good sleep could be slight chance of dozing during TV watching or predictor of sleepiness problem could be sitting inactive in a public place. Implication on Rehabilitation: Clinical manifestations of TOS affected more the quality of sleeping than on sleepiness, which means that there is a need for more research in this direction.

PO-1343

REHABILITATING CLAW-THUMB BY RECONSTRUCTIVE SURGERY (OPPONENSPLASTY) IN LEPROSY CURED PATIENTS

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